

From Cosmos to Theos – Towards a New Philosophical Theology

[From Cosmos to Theos – Towards a New Philosophical Theology.
Joseph Mathew. Media House, Delhi. 2017. xvii+297]

- Augustine Pamplany

From Cosmos to Theosis by Joseph Mathew is a unique blend of cosmological scholarship with creative hermeneutical appropriation. The brilliant hermeneutical skills employed by the author in this interdisciplinary work draws up several original insights even from traditional themes. The book is an immense contribution to advancing the science-religion dialogue to fresh domains, particularly in cosmological sciences. Probably this is the first of its kind from India that explores the philosophical and religious implications of the contemporary cosmology in such depth and magnitude.

It was Einstein who said that most of the ideas of science are essentially simple and may be formulated in a language comprehensible to the ordinary people. Prof. Joseph Mathew's writings literally embodies the observation of Einstein. The author belongs to a rare breed of writers who insightfully combines the academic and the popular, the scientific and the narrative, the rational and the intuitive. As the author himself comments of the literary style: "From prologue to epilogue, the book develops like a story, with many plots and numerous subplots, all connected in logical sequence without leaps or gaps." It requires an extra ingenuity to carry a profound scientific field like cosmology to such a narrative style. Certainly, the long decades of teaching experience of the au-

thor has significantly contributed to the literary style of the book. It looks going through *From Cosmos to Theos* is both a *listening* as well as *reading*. It appears that the writer is vitally present on each page with an eloquent voice.

Yet another tribute to *From Cosmos to Theos* is that no scholarly critique can identify any traits of the common conceptual and epistemic pitfalls that are likely to be present in a normal interdisciplinary project. Many interdisciplinary ventures, particularly those at the intersection between science and religion invoke the mistakes of drawing one to one parallels or cooking up too many ideas employing crude hermeneutics. Prof. Thomas Mathew passes every methodological test of epistemology and hermeneutics in drawing up his original insights upholding the integrity of both disciplines. His methodic fidelity to science, philosophy and theology does not desist him from attempting profound synthesis between science, philosophy and theology. In that regard he deserves to be called a faithful scientist, a rational theologian and a courageous hermeneutician. The author has ventured into exploring several philosophical domains of the contemporary cosmology from which even many contemporary scientists have shied out.

The unique strand of conceptual progress from the epistemic through the empirical to the hermeneutical can be seen in the structure of the book. Even the fresh readers who are alien to the categories of philosophy, theology and philosophy are made feel at home with the clarifications of the essential concepts and in the first part of the book. The narrative of the first part titled, "New Frontiers in Philosophical Theology" places the reader eventually on a new logical and epistemic platform from which he/she will be appropriating the subsequent sections. The marvels of modern cosmology covering up its origin and evolution, fine-tuning, the anthropic principle, the allusions to the mysteries of life, etc., form the content of the second part titled, "From Cosmos." The synergies between science, philosophy and theology attempted by the author in the third part concludes by the rational postulation of a Cosmic Designer. Unlike the usual pattern of argument to use science as a proof for a metaphysical reality, the author has re-

versed the order by dwelling on the metaphysical aspects of the modern science complemented by the Eastern mystical traditions. Of particular mention is the recourse to the quantum conceptualities and the intuitive wisdom of the Upanishads in developing the metaphysical synthesis of the author in a scientifically informed, logically legitimate and conceptually solid manner.

The book will be an enriching reading experience to every seeker of truth who is prepared to ask the fundamental questions concerning the meaning existence, life and the universe. It is an academic entertainment as well as an intellectual provocation. The academic community owes a special debt of gratitude to the author for bringing out this scholarly product.